

FOOD PACKAGING PAPERS BASED ON BIOPOLYMERS POLYELECTROLYTE COMPLEXES

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10008200
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Abstract: *In the context of plastic consumption reduction and environmental concerns on the production of more sustainable and circular packaging, the cellulosic based materials (paper and board) are considered most promising candidates largely due to the cost-effectives and their high rate of recyclability and biodegradability. Comparing with other materials, paper and boards are more resilient over a wider temperature range, are lighter and far more easily printed and to convert into containers with specified strength and stiffness. However, as food packaging material, paper has poor barrier properties for water and humidity due to the hydrophilic nature of cellulose fibers that are main component. The most currently applied technologies to improve the paper barrier properties to be adequate for food packaging applications consist of coatings with synthetic polymers and lamination with plastic or aluminium foils. Concerning on sustainability and circularity, these technologies have negative impact, having low recyclability and biodegradability rate. From these reasons there are opportunities and challenges for cellulose based packaging materials to design the appropriate barrier and active antimicrobial properties to reach the market performances expectations without impairing their recyclability and biodegradability. The biopolymers are attracting increased attention because they not only replace the synthetic polymers in different applications but also can provide new combinations of properties and can act as matrix for embed the active components to impart functional properties when are used in food packaging applications (i.e. antimicrobial or antioxidant features). In this context, the paper presents the results on utilization of xylan hemicelluloses and their acetylated derivatives as single biopolymer or as polyelectrolyte complexes by ionic interactions with other biopolymers such as chitosan polysaccharide. The*

*polyelectrolyte complexes were used as coatings in single and multilayers for paper surface treatments (about 5 g/m²) in order to improve their barrier properties to water, water vapours, oxygen, oil and grease. The obtained results showed that for the papers coated with 50:50-acetylated xylan/chitosan formula, the level of water contact angle was about 92.8°, the water vapours transmission rate (WVTR) was about 30 g/m².day and grease resistance was at KIT 8. These are comparable with reported results for flourochemicals treated papers. In addition, the papers coated with acetylated xylan and chitosan exhibited the high inhibition capacity against gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and fungi as *Penicillium sp.* and *Aspergillus sp.* The positive results obtained in this paper provide guidelines for obtaining of new food packaging materials produced from renewable resources which can be recycled or degraded without leaving contaminants or toxic residues into the environment. Acknowledgement: This work was supported by a grant of the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitization, CNCS—UEFISCDI, project number PN-III-P4-PCE-2021-0714, within PNCDI III.*